

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Annex to Deliverable D4.1: ECHOES Consultation Questionnaire

HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01

Horizon Innovation action

Responsible authors: Claudio Prandoni – ARIADNE, Rémi Petitcol – FSP, Charlotte Gallini – FSP, Isabelle Pallot-Frossard – FSP, Sophia Sotiropoulou – FORTH, Elis Marçal – ECCO, Mailane Messias-Sampaio – CNRS, Carlos Andujar – UPC, Ruven Pillay – C2RMF, FSP, Kerstin Arnold – APEF, Andreas Georgopoulos – ICOMOS, Francesca Frontini – CNR

Project start	1 June 2024
Project duration	60 months
Document Identifier	

**Funded by
the European Union**

**UK Research
and Innovation**

ECHOES is a project funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement n.101157364, with the support of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee n.10110142 & n.10110466.

© 2026 by the authors, the ECHOES consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.

ECHOES Questionnaire

eccch.eu/objectives/.

The project

ECHOES is a project funded by the European Commission and supported by UK Research and Innovation. ECHOES' mission is to set up the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) (<https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/>), a shared platform designed to facilitate collaboration among heritage professionals and researchers, enabling them to modernise their workflows and processes. Learn more about it here (<https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/objectives/>).

The ECHOES Consultation

Welcome to the ECHOES Consultation! This questionnaire seeks to understand how various communities working with cultural heritage use digital tools in their daily practice. Your responses will help shape the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage, a platform designed to facilitate collaboration among heritage professionals and researchers, enabling them to modernise their workflows and processes. The ECHOES Consultation's objective is to identify and map the very diverse communities working on cultural heritage and to identify their needs and expectations for the Cultural Heritage Cloud. It will be initiated by the following questionnaire, complemented with workshops, focus groups and targeted interviews.

The questionnaire

As the first step of the Consultation, the questionnaire aims to identify the different heritage professionals and researchers and how they use digital tools in their daily practice. It is an adapted version of the work of the French EquipEx+ project ESPADON (<https://espadon.net/>) and builds on mapping approaches developed by several other partners or initiatives such as E-RIHS (<https://www.e-rihs.eu/>), ARIADNE RI (<https://www.ariadne-research-infrastructure.eu/>), CLARIN (<https://www.clarin.eu/>), and PERCEIVE (<https://perceive-horizon.eu/>).

Who can contribute

At this stage, the Consultation is open to all cultural heritage stakeholders working in the cultural heritage sector who are interested in the development and use of the ECCCH. Stakeholders include all professionals and individuals whose work or research focuses on cultural heritage in its wider sense. Umbrella organisations active in the field are particularly important for the Consultation, considering the wide network they will be able to mobilise.

Deadline

The questionnaire will be open until the **end of April 2025**.

Next steps

Publication of the *ECHOES Report on the identification of communities and their needs* and the *Strategy for community building*. Organisation of other community and capacity-building activities, as well as follow-up, targeted thematic interviews or surveys.

Your answers will be used solely for the purpose of this consultation and will remain confidential.

The questionnaire consists of 9 sections:

Section A helps us better understand your professional profile.

Section B focuses on the various types of heritage you might work on.

Section C allows us to gather feedback on your digital practices and needs.

Section D focuses on your data creation and re-use practices.

Section E explores your involvement in collaborations and workflows concerning data management tools.

Section F is dedicated to your practices, methods, and technologies related to data management systems and server infrastructures.

Section G allows you to request to be contacted again for further involvement in the ECHOES project.

Please note that although some questions are more technical, we strongly encourage and value your answers. We have included "No", "Not applicable" or "I don't know" options to cater to a wide range of uses and practices. These answers are valuable to us as they enable us to understand potential knowledge gaps. These results will be analysed and will inform our capacity-building and training strategy to enhance digital literacy for future Cloud users.

General information about the questionnaire

- Some sections and questions are optional and will be displayed depending on your answers to previous questions.
- This questionnaire enables you to save your progress and resume later. You can select "Save and resume later" at the bottom of the page. You will be asked to choose a username and a password. To resume the questionnaire, you can click on the three lines on the top right corner of the page. This option is accessible on computers and smart phones.

There are 75 questions in this survey.

Part A: Professional profile of the respondent

This part of the questionnaire aims to better identify and map the federated communities of users, professionals and researchers working on cultural heritage in any way. Understanding the demographics and sociology of the respondents will help the ECHOES project better orient and tailor its tools, services, communication and training materials. It will also help us identify potential gaps in representativity, which we will try to bridge through complementary activities within the Consultation such as workshops, focus groups and interviews.

A1. Please indicate whether you are answering: *

🗳 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- In your own capacity
- As a representative of an institution

A1.1. How do you identify yourself? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'In your own capacity' at question ' [A1]' (A1. Please indicate whether you are answering:)

🗳 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

A1.2. What is your age group? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'In your own capacity' at question ' [A1]' (A1. Please indicate whether you are answering:)

🗳 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 18-25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- 46-55
- 56-65
- 66-80
- Older than 80
- Prefer not to say

A1.3. What is your level of education?

If you are a student, please select your current level of education. Otherwise, please select your highest level of education.

*

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'In your own capacity' at question ' [A1]' (A1. Please indicate whether you are answering:)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- High school diploma
- Bachelor
- Masters
- Doctorate
- Other (vocational degree, professional certificates, trade school, etc.)

A1.4. Where are you based? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'In your own capacity' at question ' [A1]' (A1. Please indicate whether you are answering:)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Afghanistan
- Albania
- Algeria
- Andorra
- Angola
- Antigua and Barbuda
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Azores
- Bahamas
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bhutan
- Bolivia
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Brazil
- Brunei
- Bulgaria
- Burkina
- Burundi
- Cambodia
- Cameroon
- Canada
- Cape Verde
- Central African Rep
- Chad
- Chile
- China
- Colombia
- Comoros
- Congo
- Costa Rica
- Croatia

- Cuba
- Cyprus
- Czech Republic
- Democratic Republic of the Congo
- Denmark
- Djibouti
- Dominica
- Dominican Republic
- East Timor
- Ecuador
- Egypt
- El Salvador
- Equatorial Guinea
- Eritrea
- Estonia
- Ethiopia
- Fiji
- Finland
- France
- Gabon
- Gambia
- Georgia
- Germany
- Ghana
- Greece
- Grenada
- Guatemala
- Guinea
- Guinea-Bissau
- Guyana
- Haiti
- Honduras
- Hungary
- Iceland
- India
- Indonesia
- Iran
- Iraq
- Ireland
- Israel
- Italy
- Ivory Coast
- Jamaica
- Japan
- Jordan
- Kazakhstan
- Kenya
- Kiribati

- Korea North
- Korea South
- Kosovo
- Kuwait
- Kyrgyzstan
- Laos
- Latvia
- Lebanon
- Lesotho
- Liberia
- Libya
- Liechtenstein
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Macedonia
- Madagascar
- Malawi
- Malaysia
- Maldives
- Mali
- Malta
- Marshall Islands
- Mauritania
- Mauritius
- Mexico
- Micronesia
- Moldova
- Monaco
- Mongolia
- Montenegro
- Morocco
- Mozambique
- Myanmar
- Namibia
- Nauru
- Nepal
- Netherlands
- New Zealand
- Nicaragua
- Niger
- Nigeria
- Norway
- Oman
- Pakistan
- Palau
- Panama
- Papua New Guinea
- Paraguay

- Peru
- Philippines
- Poland
- Portugal
- Qatar
- Romania
- Russian Federation
- Rwanda
- Saint Kitts & Nevis
- Saint Lucia
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
- Samoa
- San Marino
- Sao Tome and Principe
- Saudi Arabia
- Senegal
- Serbia
- Seychelles
- Sierra Leone
- Singapore
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Solomon Islands
- Somalia
- South Africa
- South Sudan
- Spain
- Sri Lanka
- Sudan
- Suriname
- Swaziland
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Syria
- Taiwan
- Tajikistan
- Tanzania
- Thailand
- Togo
- Tonga
- Trinidad and Tobago
- Tunisia
- Turkey
- Turkmenistan
- Tuvalu
- Uganda
- Ukraine
- United Arab Emirates

- United Kingdom
- United States
- Uruguay
- Uzbekistan
- Vanuatu
- Vatican City
- Venezuela
- Vietnam
- Yemen
- Zambia
- Zimbabwe

A1.1. Where is your institution based? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'As a representative of an institution' at question ' [A1]' (A1. Please indicate whether you are answering:)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Afghanistan
- Albania
- Algeria
- Andorra
- Angola
- Antigua and Barbuda
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Azores
- Bahamas
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bhutan
- Bolivia
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Brazil
- Brunei
- Bulgaria
- Burkina
- Burundi
- Cambodia
- Cameroon
- Canada
- Cape Verde
- Central African Rep
- Chad
- Chile
- China
- Colombia
- Comoros
- Congo
- Costa Rica
- Croatia

- Cuba
- Cyprus
- Czech Republic
- Democratic Republic of the Congo
- Denmark
- Djibouti
- Dominica
- Dominican Republic
- East Timor
- Ecuador
- Egypt
- El Salvador
- Equatorial Guinea
- Eritrea
- Estonia
- Ethiopia
- Fiji
- Finland
- France
- Gabon
- Gambia
- Georgia
- Germany
- Ghana
- Greece
- Grenada
- Guatemala
- Guinea
- Guinea-Bissau
- Guyana
- Haiti
- Honduras
- Hungary
- Iceland
- India
- Indonesia
- Iran
- Iraq
- Ireland
- Israel
- Italy
- Ivory Coast
- Jamaica
- Japan
- Jordan
- Kazakhstan
- Kenya
- Kiribati

- Korea North
- Korea South
- Kosovo
- Kuwait
- Kyrgyzstan
- Laos
- Latvia
- Lebanon
- Lesotho
- Liberia
- Libya
- Liechtenstein
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Macedonia
- Madagascar
- Malawi
- Malaysia
- Maldives
- Mali
- Malta
- Marshall Islands
- Mauritania
- Mauritius
- Mexico
- Micronesia
- Moldova
- Monaco
- Mongolia
- Montenegro
- Morocco
- Mozambique
- Myanmar
- Namibia
- Nauru
- Nepal
- Netherlands
- New Zealand
- Nicaragua
- Niger
- Nigeria
- Norway
- Oman
- Pakistan
- Palau
- Panama
- Papua New Guinea
- Paraguay

- Peru
- Philippines
- Poland
- Portugal
- Qatar
- Romania
- Russian Federation
- Rwanda
- Saint Kitts & Nevis
- Saint Lucia
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
- Samoa
- San Marino
- Sao Tome and Principe
- Saudi Arabia
- Senegal
- Serbia
- Seychelles
- Sierra Leone
- Singapore
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Solomon Islands
- Somalia
- South Africa
- South Sudan
- Spain
- Sri Lanka
- Sudan
- Suriname
- Swaziland
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Syria
- Taiwan
- Tajikistan
- Tanzania
- Thailand
- Togo
- Tonga
- Trinidad and Tobago
- Tunisia
- Turkey
- Turkmenistan
- Tuvalu
- Uganda
- Ukraine
- United Arab Emirates

- United Kingdom
- United States
- Uruguay
- Uzbekistan
- Vanuatu
- Vatican City
- Venezuela
- Vietnam
- Yemen
- Zambia
- Zimbabwe

A1.2. What is the name of the institution you work for:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'As a representative of an institution' at question ' [A1]' (A1. Please indicate whether you are answering:)

Please write your answer here:

A2. What is your current working status?

🗖 Check all that apply

🗖 Please select from 1 to 3 answers.

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Business owner / Entrepreneur
- Employed
- Self-employed / Freelancer
- Student
- Unemployed / Job-seeking
- Volunteer
- Other

A3. What is your current occupation?

Please specify your role(s), your field of study (if you're a student), and/or your job title (if you're employed).

Please write your answer here:

A4. Do you work for: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Volunteer' or 'Self-employed / Freelancer' or 'Employed' or 'Business owner / Entrepreneur' at question ' [A2]' (A2. What is your current working status?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- A private non-profit organisation
- A public non-profit organisation
- A private for-profit organisation
- A public for-profit organisation

A5. What type of institution / organisation / company do you work for: *

🗳️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- LAM (library, archive, museum)
- University, research institute or research infrastructure
- Governmental agency or other public authority
- Historical monuments, listed buildings, sites
- Company or other type of for-profit organisation (including workshops)
- Professional or trade association
- Gallery or exhibition space
- Other:

A6. Which of the following best describes your professional activity or the field(s) in which your work primarily fits? *

🗳️ Check all that apply

🗳️ Please select from 1 to 3 answers.

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Cultural heritage conservation and preservation** (includes conservation-restoration, heritage crafts, heritage protection, and preventive conservation)
- Museology and collection management** (includes curation, exhibition management, cataloguing, scenography)
- Documentation, archives, and information management** (includes library and information science and management)
- Artistic creation and art market** (includes artistic creation, art criticism, creative industry, art market)
- Education, mediation and audience engagement** (includes cultural education, teaching, heritage interpretation, audience development, communication, publishing)
- Digital technologies and data management** (IT infrastructure provisioning, imaging science, metadata creation, digital preservation, digitisation (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digitization>), data management)
- Management, policy, governance and exploitation** (policy-making, project management, advocacy, risk assessment, management and mitigation; law, law enforcement, tourism, CCIs)
- Urban and spatial planning** (architecture, landscape architecture, urban and spatial planning)
- Research and studies in social sciences and humanities** (anthropology, ethnology, sociology, semiotics, philosophy, linguistics, history, art history, archaeology, musicology, literature, economics)
- Science, engineering and applied research** (computer science, ICT technologies, chemistry, physics, engineering, archaeometry, conservation sciences)
- Other** (research)

A7. In your daily practice, what fields of expertise do you deal with even if you are not an expert?

The following categories are part of the *ERC Field Classification* (<https://ejoss.euras-edu.org/erc-field-classification/>). By linking your field of research with one of the following categories, we are striving to harmonise some of the results of this questionnaire with existing European research structures and initiatives.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Other (research)' or 'Science, engineering and applied research (computer science, ICT technologies, chemistry, physics, engineering, archaeometry, conservation sciences)' or 'Research and studies in social sciences and humanities (anthropology, ethnology, sociology, semiotics, philosophy, linguistics, history, art history, archaeology, musicology, literature, economics)' at question ' [A6]' (A6. Which of the following best describes your professional activity or the field(s) in which your work primarily fits?)

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Humanities and Social Sciences** (includes Culture, Economics, Policy and Governance, Urban planning, etc.)
- Life Sciences** (includes Environmental science, Biology, Neurosciences, etc.)
- Physical Sciences and Engineering** (includes Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Computer Science, etc.)

A8. Are you involved in national, European or international projects related to Digital Cultural Heritage or any other project relevant to the Cultural Heritage Cloud?

Here we refer to any type of project including scientific research projects, conservation-restoration projects, cooperation on touring exhibitions, etc. "Digital Cultural Heritage" refers to digital-born heritage as well as any project focusing on the digitisation of heritage, its study and documentation through digital tools or projects relating to the digital dimension of heritage. Collaborative projects are included.

*

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- National
- European
- International
- Not applicable

A8.1. Which one(s)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'International' or 'European' or 'National' at question ' [A8]' (A8. Are you involved in national, European or international projects related to Digital Cultural Heritage or any other project relevant to the Cultural Heritage Cloud? Here we refer to any type of project including scientific research projects, conservation-restoration projects, cooperation on touring exhibitions, etc. "Digital Cultural Heritage" refers to digital-born heritage as well as any project focusing on the digitisation of heritage, its study and documentation through digital tools or projects relating to the digital dimension of heritage. Collaborative projects are included.)

Please write your answer here:

Please provide a link, if possible.

Part B: Areas of expertise and focus in cultural heritage

This part aims to understand the fields on which Cultural Heritage communities focus. The objective is to contribute to the identification and mapping of these communities through their work. This will, in turn, contribute to a better understanding of the communities and their needs, particularly in terms of digital literacy, workflows and training.

*For the purpose of this survey, "Heritage" must be understood broadly and includes tangible, intangible, cultural, natural, (born-)digital
(<http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/information-management/manage-information/digital-records-transfer/what-are-born-digital-records/>).*

B1. Which types of heritage assets (https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-3-319-31816-5_2274-1) do you work with? *

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Textual resources** (https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/resource#google_vignette):
- Journal / Magazine / Other Periodicals
- Manuscript
- Printed Book
- Records and archives
- Other type of textual resource
- Visual Resources:**
- 3D models
- Cinema
- Comics/Illustrations
- Drawing / Sketches
- Map / Atlas
- Other type of visual resource (ex: games)
- Painting
- Photograph
- Print (including engraving)
- Objects:**
- Archaeological artefact
- Detached architectural element
- Other decorative arts
- Scientific or educational instrument, object or machine
- Sculpture
- Textile
- Other type of movable heritage
- Spatial design and built spaces:**
- Architecture
- Garden
- Historical and Archaeological Site
- Installation (including art installations and exhibition design)
- Landscape
- Urban complex
- Other type of architectural work, built space, and developed spaces
- Other Heritage Resources on Physical Media:**
- Audio Resource
- Multimedia Resource
- Video Resource
- Other types of resources on physical media
- Natural Resources / Naturalia:**
- Herbaria
- Mineral and Geological
- Palaeontological
- Zoological
- Intangible Heritage:**
- Knowledge and practices
- Oral traditions and expressions
- Performing arts
- Social practices

Traditional craftsmanship

Other:

Entries in bold refer to general categories. Other entries refer to specific types of assets.

B2. Which of the following do you mostly use in your work? *

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Physical objects** (e.g. artworks, sites, natural specimens, ...)
- Non-digital reproductions** (e.g., printed photos, casts, or other physical replicas of the object)
- Multimedia assets** (e.g., audio recordings, videos, or interactive media related to the object)
- Digital representations** (e.g., digitised versions of objects, such as high-resolution scans, photographs, or 3D models)
- Born-digital assets**

B3. What is the geographical provenance of the heritage assets you work on? *

🗨️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Europe
- Americas
- Africa
- Oceania
- Asia
- Antarctica
- Not applicable

Part C: Digital tools and resources: current needs and practices

This section explores your current use of digital tools (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/tool>) and resources and the need for their improvement.

If a question does not apply to you, you may skip it by selecting 'No,' 'Don't know,' or 'Not applicable.' All responses—whether complete, partial, or negative—are valuable for understanding training and capacity-building needs. If you have any concerns or specific needs, please share them in the "free text" boxes provided.

C1.1a. Are you using data (<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/data#English>) annotation and analysis (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/data_analysis_18) tools or services (<https://vocabs.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/archecategory/service>)? *

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Not yet, but I would like to use them

C1.1b. I use or would like to use: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' or 'Not yet, but I would like to use them' at question ' [C1s1a]' (C1.1a. Are you using data annotation and analysis tools or services?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Tools for manual annotation of digital assets (text, image, audio, 3D, etc.)
- Automated content analysis of speech and textual resources (NLP, machine translation, etc.)
- Handwriting Recognition (HTR) / Optical Character Recognition (OCR)
- Automatic shape / texture recognition

C1.2a. Are you using 3D modeling (<https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/modeling>) and visualisation tools or services? *

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Not yet, but I would like to use them

C1.2b. I use or would like to use: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' or 'Not yet, but I would like to use them' at question ' [C1s2a]' (C1.2a. Are you using 3D modeling and visualisation tools or services?)

🗳️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- 3D scanning or modeling, rendering ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rendering_\(computer_graphics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rendering_(computer_graphics))) and reconstruction
- Building Information Modeling (BIM/HBIM)
- Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging (LIDAR)
- Geographic Information System (GIS), spatial representation of information
- Virtual Reality (VR) / Augmented Reality (AR) / Mixed Reality (MR)

C1.3a. Are you using data management and storage tools or services? *

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Not yet, but I would like to use them

C1.3b. I use or would like to use: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' or 'Not yet, but I would like to use them' at question ' [C1s3a]' (C1.3a. Are you using data management and storage tools or services?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Resource storage and retrieval systems
- Data collection management and structuring
- Data interoperability and API integration

C1.4a. Are you using formal knowledge representation tools or services? *

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Not yet, but I would like to use them

C1.4b. I use or would like to use: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' or 'Not yet, but I would like to use them' at question ' [C1s4a]' (C1.4a. Are you using formal knowledge representation tools or services?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Taxonomies and controlled vocabularies
- Ontologies
- Knowledge graphs, semantic web technologies and linked data

C2. What difficulties, if any, do you encounter when using digital tools and resources for your work? How do these affect your ability to achieve your goals?

For example: learning curve, compatibility and integration issues, data security and privacy concerns, dependency on internet connectivity, costs, technical issues, unresponsive customer support, lack of user-friendliness, etc.

Please write your answer here:

C3. In what ways could these tools and services be improved? Are there any specific functionalities or improvements you would find helpful?

This question relates to the tools you are currently using or developing and will feed into the roadmap for implementing Cloud tools and services.

Please write your answer here:

C4. Which type of access models do you currently use for digital tools and services?

Please answer to the best of your knowledge. If you are not aware of any fees, subscriptions or limitations of use, please select the first option.

*

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Free, open-access services** (e.g., no cost, no subscription required, no limitation on use)
- Free with a license** (e.g., free-to-use with specific terms, or optional paid features, e.g., limited functionality unless upgraded)
- Trial-based access** (limited-time or feature-limited access before purchase)
- Paid subscription-based services** (e.g., monthly or annual fees)
- Paid licence-based services** (e.g., one-time purchase or perpetual licenses)
- Pay-per-use / usage-based access** (charges based on usage, e.g., number of queries, resources consumed)
- Developed in-house or custom-built tools** (e.g., software created by your organisation)
- Open-source software** (freely available to download, modify and distribute)

Other:

C5. What are your main objectives when using the tools? If you are a researcher, what are the research questions you aim to address using the tools?

Please write your answer here:

C6. How do you typically log in or authenticate when accessing digital tools and services? *

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Apple ID
- EduGAIN
- EUlogin
- Facebook
- Google
- Institutional Login (log in using your organisation's credentials)
- Microsoft
- ORCID
- Other enterprise Single Sign-On (SSO)

Part D: Description of the data you create, consult or reuse

This part focuses on the types of primary data (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/primary_data_175) you are currently creating and secondary (<http://data.loterre.fr/ark:/67375/TSO-D80R1KX4-5>)(existing) data you consult or use in your research and/or professional activities.

Do not hesitate to share any doubts, concerns or thoughts you might have about these topics in the "free text" box provided.

D1. What processes do you typically use to produce data? *

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Archival research** (e.g., consulting historical records, documents, or archives)
- Digitisation, transcription and 3D and spatial documentation**
- Computational methods** (e.g., simulations, algorithms, or modeling)
- Crowdsourcing or citizen science** (e.g., engaging non-specialists to gather data)
- Examination / analysis** (e.g., visual inspection, instrumental analysis, laboratory testing, material analysis and testing, imaging and spectroscopy methods)
- Experimental methods** (e.g., controlled experiments or trials, material reconstructions, accelerated ageing tests)
- Fieldwork** (e.g., on-site data collection or acquisition, conservation treatment documentation and monitoring)
- Interviews or focus groups** (e.g., qualitative data collection through discussion)
- Observation** (e.g., direct or indirect observation of phenomena or processes)
- Processing data / resources created by others or reprocessing your own primary data** (e.g., data reanalysis, comparative studies, data aggregation and enrichment, transformation, modeling, interpretation, synthesis or fusion)
- Surveys / questionnaires** (e.g., collecting data through participant responses)
- Other:

D2. What are the primary objectives of producing data in your work? *

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Answering research questions** (e.g., contributing to academic or scientific studies, such as material characterisation, provenance study, etc.)
- Archiving** (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/data_archiving_21) or **preserving information** (e.g., maintaining records for future reference)
- Cataloguing information** (e.g., metadata creation for management or reporting purposes)
- Creating conservation or restoration plans** (e.g., documenting objects for heritage preservation, condition reports)
- Developing educational materials** (e.g., creating resources for teaching or training)
- Monitoring and evaluation** (e.g., tracking progress or assessing impact)
- Preparing reports** (e.g., internal reports, technical documentation, or project summaries)
- Public communication or awareness** (e.g., sharing findings with a general audience)
- Supporting decision-making** (e.g., providing insights for strategic planning or policy-making)
- Other:

D3. What types of data do you typically create, consult or reuse? *

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Administrative or regulatory records** (government data, legal information, regulations)
- Biological or genomic information** (DNA sequences, biological samples, genetic data)
- Descriptive metadata** (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/metadata_158)(summaries or categorisations of datasets (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/data_set_113))
- Environmental measurements** (data from ecological monitoring or natural systems)
- Experimental results** (outcomes from controlled, reproducible experiments)
- Historical or archival records** (legacy information, records from the past)
- Machine-generated insights** (automated logs, data from sensors or IoT devices)
- Observational findings** (field notes, natural observations, event logs)
- Published research outputs** (previously disseminated academic or scientific findings)
- Quantitative data** (numerical data, statistics, measured values)
- Social or behavioural information** (data from social networks, behavioural studies)
- Spatial / geographical information** (location-based data, maps, geographic features)
- Structural or spatial representations** (conceptual models, spatial relationships)
- Survey and interview responses** (data from consultations, interviews, or polls)
- Textual or written information** (e.g., narratives, documentation, reports, articles)
- Other:

D4. What data types and formats do you commonly use?

This question refers to the data you produce, consult or reuse the most in your daily activities when working on Cultural Heritage.

*

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- 3D models and renders** (e.g., OBJ, STL, PLY, 3DS, GLTF, VRML)
- Archived or compression formats** (e.g., ZIP, TAR)
- Audio files** (e.g., MP3, WAV)
- Code or scripts** (e.g., Python .py, SQL .sql, R, MATLAB .m, JavaScript .js, Jupyter .ipynb)
- Databases** (e.g., SQL, NoSQL, SQLite, relational, non-relational)
- Document formats** (PDF, RTF, Word files, LaTeX)
- Geospatial data formats** (GeoJSON, Shapefile (SHP), KML, GML)
- Image formats** (JPEG/JPG, PNG, TIFF, JPEG2000, SVG)
- Video formats** (MP4, MKV, AVI)
- Presentations** (e.g., PowerPoint, Keynote)
- Spreadsheets** (e.g., Excel, ODS)
- Statistical and analytical dataset formats** (SAV (SPSS), RData, HDF5, NetCDF)
- Streaming data formats** (AVRO, Parquet, Protobuf, Kafka, WebSocket, MQTT, RTSP, HLS)
- Text-based formats** (TXT, CSV, JSON, XML, RDF, YAML, XMP)
- Web formats and renders** (e.g., HTML, JavaScript, SVG, JSON-LD, HTML5 Video/Audio, WebVR/WebAR, live streams)
- Other:

D5. Does your institution follow a published Data Management Plan (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/data_management_plan_6)

*

📌 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

D5.1. Please provide the URL if available:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [D5]' (D5. Does your institution follow a published Data Management Plan?)

Please write your answer here:

D6. Do you mainly use open or closed formats?

An open format refers to a type of format that is encoded transparently and are interoperable.

A closed or proprietary format (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Proprietary_file_format) can only be read by specific software.

*

🗨 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Open formats
- Closed / proprietary formats
- Both
- I don't know

D7. Do you process (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/data_processing_82) or analyse the data you produce yourself? *

🗨 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- Sometimes
- No

D7.1. How? With which software(s)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' or 'Sometimes' at question ' [D7]' (D7. Do you process or analyse the data you produce yourself?)

Please write your answer here:

D8. Do you document the data you produce (with explanatory notes, annotations, metadata, etc.)? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

D8.1. How do you typically document the data you produce? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [D8]' (D8. Do you document the data you produce (with explanatory notes, annotations, metadata, etc.)?)

🗳 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Simple notes (e.g., handwritten or digital notes)
- Annotations (e.g., marking up files or adding comments directly to data)
- Manual documentation (e.g., creating standalone documentation files)
- Using a documentation system (e.g., a structured platform for documenting data)
- Filling in metadata (e.g., adding descriptive information such as titles, keywords, or provenance)
- Following established standards (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technical_standard) or protocols (e.g., domain-specific standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM)
- Automated systems (e.g., systems that auto-generate documentation or metadata embedded in or linked to the data files)
- Using controlled vocabularies (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/controlled_vocabulary_11) (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)

Other:

D8.1.1. Please list the controlled vocabularies you use, with their URL whenever possible: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Using controlled vocabularies (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/controlled_vocabulary_11) (e.g., Getty AAT, other thematic thesauri, local vocabularies, CEN TC 346, etc.)' at question ' [D8s1]' (D8.1. How do you typically document the data you produce?)

Please write your answer here:

D9. Where do you typically store or archive the data you create (primary datasets (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/primary_data_175))? *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part of data (50 - 75%)	True for all or most data (76 - 100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In domain-specific repositories (e.g. Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In public archives or generic-purpose open access repositories (Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On cloud-based commercial platform (Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On institutional servers or websites (e.g. NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On self-hosted (cloud-based) servers (e.g. nextcloud/owncloud) or personal websites	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

D10. Do you share the data you produce? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, always
- Yes, sometimes
- No

D10.1. With whom do you share the data you produce? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes, always' or 'Yes, sometimes' at question ' [D10]' (D10. Do you share the data you produce?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Within my team / project
- Within my institution/organisation
- With collaborators outside my organisation
- Publicly with the broader community

D11. Please rank the following statements about the data you create: *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part of data (50 - 75%)	True for all or most data (76 - 100%)
Shared by email, direct communication, or commercial cloud-based file-sharing platforms (e.g., Google Drive, Dropbox)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Shared through publications (scientific or public), annexes of administrative documents, or other reports	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Made accessible within my institution/organisation/company repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Made accessible through a public repository or generic-purpose Open-access platforms (e.g., Zenodo, Figshare)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Made accessible through domain specific repositories (e.g., Archives Portal Europe, EUScreen)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Made accessible through digital stores (e.g. Unity Assets Store, _Fab marketplace_)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

D12. Under which conditions do you typically share your data? *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	True for no data (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part of data (50 - 75%)	True for all or most data (76 - 100%)
Openly, with no restrictions (CC0, Public Domain)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Under a specific open license (e.g., Creative Commons, ...)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
With access restrictions (e.g., password-protected or limited audiences)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Through formal agreements (e.g., data-sharing agreements, memorandums of understanding)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
After an embargo period (e.g., data is made public only after a specified time)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Upon request only	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
For specific purposes only (e.g., for research, educational use, or within a collaboration)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
After anonymisation or modification (e.g., data is cleaned, aggregated, or anonymised before sharing)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

D13. What challenges do you face when sharing, consulting or reusing data? *

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Concerns about data misuse
- Confidentiality or privacy concerns (including GDPR compliance when data refers to specific persons, e.g. archival material)
- Data or metadata quality, reliability, completeness
- Extra effort is required, lack of time or resources to prepare data for sharing
- Lack of appropriate infrastructure or platforms for sharing
- Legal or contractual restrictions, intellectual property rights / other legal issues
- Non-digital data, resource is not digitised
- Technical barriers (e.g., difficulty accessing or using the required tools or platforms, large format files unable to be shared by common open means)
- Unclear guidelines regarding sharing

 Other:

D14. What is your objective when you produce, consult or reuse data? *

🗨️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- To conduct new analyses or generate new insights, generate more comprehensive interpretations of heritage materials, to apply machine learning or AI to extract new insights
- To improve dataset completeness, establish best practices for heritage data collection and analysis
- To validate hypotheses or verify findings, compare with current datasets or other sources of information, or identify new patterns, trends, or connections in the data
- To develop or refine tools, algorithms or models for prediction or data interpretation, digital visualisation and representation of heritage
- To use data for wider public engagement and educational purposes, develop teaching resources and case studies
- To support the management and protection of heritage assets, inform conservation strategies and interventions, provide evidence to influence cultural heritage policies
- To support cultural industries, or economic activities related to heritage, create virtual or augmented reality experiences
- Other:

D15. Do you reuse your own data? Are you the main author of the data you reuse? *

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I never reuse my old data (0%)
- Yes, for some of my projects (< 50%)
- Yes, for a large part of my projects (50 - 75%)
- Yes, for all or most of my projects (76 - 100%)

D16. Where do you typically access the data you consult or reuse (secondary dataset (<http://data.loterre.fr/ark:/67375/TSO-D80R1KX4-5>))? *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Not true at all (0%)	True for some data (< 50%)	True for a large part of data (50 - 75%)	True for all or most data (76 - 100%)
Locally (e.g., on a personal computer, hard drive, USB key, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In domain-specific repositories (e.g., Europeana, Artstor, CLARIN Centres)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In public archives or generic-purpose open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo, HAL, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On a cloud-based commercial platform (e.g., Google Drive, Dropbox, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Subscription-based platforms (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On institutional or private servers or websites (e.g., NAS, etc., organisation or university-managed storage or website)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaborative platforms (e.g., GitHub, Wikidata)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social networks or forums (e.g., ResearchGate, Academia.edu)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Part E: Involvement in software, tools or digital services development

This part focuses on your involvement in the development of software, tools, and digital services. We are interested in any form of involvement, whether as a programmer or simply as a tester. If you are not involved in these activities, you will be able to skip to the next part of the questionnaire.

Do not hesitate to share any doubts, concerns or thoughts you might have about these topics in the "free text" box provided.

E1. Are you involved in the development of software, digital tools or services? *

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

E2. What is your level of involvement in the development of such tools? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [E1]' (E1. Are you involved in the development of software, digital tools or services?)

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Occasional contributor (e.g., providing feedback, testing)
- Frequent contributor (e.g., suggesting features, enrichment, collaborating in development)
- Primary developer (e.g., coding, designing core functionalities)
- Project manager or coordinator (e.g., overseeing development, setting objectives)
- Other:

E3. What is your primary role in the development of such tools? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [E1]' (E1. Are you involved in the development of software, digital tools or services?)

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- End-user / tester (e.g., using tools, providing requirements and feedback)
- Concept designer (e.g., defining objectives, features, or workflow)
- Developer / programmer (e.g., coding, scripting)
- Data scientist / analyst (e.g., integrating analysis needs into tool design)
- Project manager / coordinator (e.g., overseeing the development process)
- Other:

E4. What are the types of tools? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [E1]' (E1. Are you involved in the development of software, digital tools or services?)

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Data analysis tools
- Data interpretation tools
- Data enrichment tools
- Domain-specific tools
- Other:

E5. Please provide the URL if available:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [E1]' (E1. Are you involved in the development of software, digital tools or services?)

Please write your answer here:

E6. How do you collaborate with the development teams? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [E1]' (E1. Are you involved in the development of software, digital tools or services?)

🗨️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Regular meetings and feedback sessions
- Using collaborative tools like Slack, Trello, or Jira, or Figma
- Through detailed requirement documentation
- Direct involvement in testing and iterative development
- Via email or written reports only
- Participation in workshops or hackathons

Other:

Part F: Involvement in the management of databases, servers or repositories

This part explores your involvement, uses and practices in the management of databases, servers and repositories. If you are not involved in these activities, you will be able to skip to the last part of the questionnaire.

Do not hesitate to share any doubts, concerns or thoughts you might have about these topics in the "free text" box provided.

F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Server_\(computing\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Server_(computing)))(s) or repository (https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshocterm/en/page/data_repository_100) (ies)? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

F2. What type of database do you manage? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

🗨️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Relational database (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Relational_database)
- Object-oriented database (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Object_database)
- Distributed database (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distributed_database)
- NoSQL database (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NoSQL>)
- Graph database (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Graph_database)

Other:

F2.1. Please provide the name(s) of the database(s):

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

Please write your answer here:

F2.2. What applications or services are associated with these databases?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

🔴 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Storage
- Querying
- Modification
- Extraction
- Visualisation
- Geolocation
- Web tools or services
- Stand-alone tools or services

Other:

F2.3. Does the database rely on an ontological model (<https://vocabs.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/dhataxonomy/Concept40.02>)? (e.g., CIDOC CRM, IFLA-LRM, etc.) *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

🔴 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

F2.3.1. What ontological models are used? Please provide URL if available:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F2s3]' (F2.3. Does the database rely on an ontological model? (e.g., CIDOC CRM, IFLA-LRM, etc.))

Please write your answer here:

F3. What type of server do you manage? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

! Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- File and storage servers
- Database servers
- Web and application servers
- Communication servers
- Network servers
- Authentication and directory servers
- Virtualisation and containerisation servers
- Development and testing servers
- Gaming and media servers
- Monitoring and logging servers
- Hybrid and cloud servers

Other:

F4. What methods and systems do you use to store, archive and curate data within your organisation? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

! Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Automation and scripting (using automated workflows and scripts to manage archiving tasks, including scheduled backups and data migration)
- Backup and redundancy (creating duplicate copies of data for safety, stored across multiple locations to ensure resilience)
- Cloud-based archiving (using cloud platforms for data storage, including general cloud services and dedicated archival solutions)
- Collaboration with trusted repositories (depositing data in recognised repositories or archives that ensure long-term preservation and accessibility)
- Data tiering and lifecycle management (managing data by moving it between storage types based on usage, transitioning from active to archival storage over time)
- Digital preservation platforms** (employing specialised tools and systems designed for long-term digital preservation and compliance with archival standards)
- Encryption and security** (protecting archived data through encryption and implementing strict access controls to ensure confidentiality and integrity)
- Institutional or enterprise systems** (archiving within organisational repositories or enterprise systems like research data centres and DAM/CMS platforms)
- Local storage solutions** (storing data on physical devices, such as external drives, NAS devices, or optical media)
- Metadata and documentation** (archiving data along with descriptive information, annotations, and contextual details for easier discovery and use)
- Periodic review and migration** (regularly reviewing archived data for obsolescence and migrating to updated formats or systems to maintain usability over time)
- Physical archiving** (maintaining physical records or media, such as printed documents, microfilm, or magnetic tapes, in secure environments)
- Standardised practices and formats** (following established protocols and using standard file formats to ensure long-term data preservation and compatibility)

Other:

F5. When choosing storage solutions, do you differentiate between 'hot data' (frequently accessed or actively used data) and 'cold data' (infrequently accessed or archival data)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

F6. Does your institution have long-term solutions for archiving data (<https://loterre.istex.fr/TSO/fr/page/-K62D86BQ-H>)? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

F7. What are the possible access methods to your servers, databases or repositories? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Internal access only - restricted to institution / organisation / company staff
- Limited access - restricted to certain professionals
- Open access - after account creation or registration
- Open access - without account creation or registration
- Access upon request

Other:

F8. What are the export options available? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [F1]' (F1. Are you involved in the management of your institution's database(s), server(s) or repository(ies)?)

🗨 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Export restricted to some data
- Complete export of descriptive field
- "Dump" type export

Other:

Part G: Let's keep in touch!

Thank you for taking the time to answer the ECHOES questionnaire!

In this part, we ask you if you'd like to stay in touch and get involved further in the project, and more specifically in the Consultation. The topics and target communities for the workshops, interviews and focus groups will depend on the results of the questionnaire. So if you'd like to have a more thorough say about what the future Cloud for Cultural Heritage should include, you can choose to be recontacted by the project team.

G1. Do you have anything to add or suggestions for the Cultural Heritage Cloud in general or for ECHOES in particular?

Please write your answer here:

G2. Would you like to receive the results from this questionnaire? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

G3. Would you like to be added to the ECHOES mailing list to receive its newsletter with updates on the project, future events and more? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

G4. Would you like to participate in other ECHOES activities (workshops, focus groups, interviews, etc)? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

G5. What is your email address? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [G2]' (G2. Would you like to receive the results from this questionnaire?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [G3]' (G3. Would you like to be added to the ECHOES mailing list to receive its newsletter with updates on the project, future events and more?)

----- or Scenario 3 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [G4]' (G4. Would you like to participate in other ECHOES activities (workshops, focus groups, interviews, etc)?)

Please write your answer here:

We sincerely thank you for taking the time to answer this questionnaire! Your answers will be very valuable to better understand the heritage communities that will constitute the users of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

If you did not agree to be recontacted but you'd still like to learn more about our future news and activities, you can visit the News & Events (<https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/news-events/>) page of the ECHOES website.

You can also follow us on LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/echoes-eu/posts/?feedView=all>), Instagram (https://www.instagram.com/echoes_eu/), Bluesky (<https://bsky.app/profile/echoes-eu.bsky.social>), Canal U (<https://www.canal-u.tv/chaines/echoes>) Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/people/European-Cloud-for-Heritage-OpEn-Science-Echoes/61554773400264/>) and X (https://x.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2Fechoes_eu).

The ECHOES Team

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.